

Scalar and Vector Space of Combinatorial Geometric Series

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Abstract: This paper discusses about the vector space of combinatorial geometric series. The coefficient for each term in combinatorial geometric series refers to a binomial coefficient. This idea can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real life problems.

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1. Introduction

When the author of this article was trying to develop the multiple summations of geometric series, a new idea stimulated his mind to create a combinatorial geometric series [1-12]. The combinatorial geometric series is a geometric series whose coefficient of each term of the geometric series denotes the binomial coefficient V_n^r . In this article, an abelian group, ring, and field [1-12] are discussed on the binomial coefficients of combinatorial geometric series.

2. Combinatorial Geometric Series

The combinatorial geometric series [1-12] is derived from the multiple summations of geometric series. The coefficient of each term in the combinatorial refers to the binomial coefficient V_n^r .

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n \cdots \sum_{i_r=i_{r-1}}^n x^{i_r} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i \quad \& \quad V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3) \cdots (n+r-1)(n+r)}{r!},$$

where $n \geq 0, r \geq 1$ and $n, r \in N = \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$.

Here, $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i$ refers to the combinatorial geometric series and

V_n^r is the binomial coefficient of combinatorial geometric series.

Let λ be a real number and $\lambda V_i^r = \mu_i$. Then μ_i is a real number for $i = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$.

i.e. $\{\mu_i \mid -\infty < \mu_i < \infty\}$ is a set of real numbers.

Let $f(x) = V_0^r + V_1^r x + V_2^r x^2 + V_3^r x^3 + \cdots + V_n^r x^n$ be a polynomial of degree $\leq n$. Then

$$\lambda f(x) = \lambda V_0^r + \lambda V_1^r x + \lambda V_2^r x^2 + \lambda V_3^r x^3 + \cdots + \lambda V_n^r x^n,$$

i.e. $\lambda f(x) = \mu_0 + \mu_0 x + \mu_0 x^2 + \mu_0 x^3 + \cdots + \mu_0 x^n$ is also a polynomial of degree $\leq n$.

3. Vector Space

Vector space is a nonempty set V of objects, called vectors, on which are defined two operations, called addition and multiplication by scalars (real numbers), subject to the following axioms. The axioms must hold for all a, b, c in V and for scalars α and β .

1. $a + b$ is in V .
2. $a + b = b + a$.
3. $a + (b + c) = (a + b) + c$.
4. There is a vector (called zero vector) 0 in V such that $a + 0 = a$.
5. For each a in V , there is a vector $-a$ in V satisfying $a + (-a) = 0$.
6. αa is in V .
7. $\alpha(a + b) = \alpha a + \alpha b$.
8. $(\alpha + \beta)a = \alpha a + \beta a$.
9. $(\alpha\beta)a = \alpha(\beta a)$.
10. $1a = a$.

Theorem 3.1: Let $n \geq 0$ be an integer and P_n be the set of polynomials of degree at most $n \geq 0$. Members of P_n have the form

$$\sum_{i=0}^n qV_i^r x^i = \sum_{i=0}^n \mu_i x^i, (rV_i^r = \mu_i \text{ for } i = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots), \text{ that is, } \mathbf{p}(x) = \sum_{i=0}^n \mu_i x^i.$$

where $\mu_i, (i = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots)$, are real numbers and x is a real variable. The nonempty set P_n is a vector space.

Proof. Let us prove this theorem using the *axioms* of vector space.

Axiom 1 (**A1**):

The polynomial $\mathbf{p} + \mathbf{q}$ is defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{p}(x) + \mathbf{q}(x) = (\mathbf{p} + \mathbf{q})x$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\Rightarrow (\mu_0 + \mu_1 x + \mu_2 x^2 + \dots + \mu_n x^n) + (\delta_0 + \delta_1 x + \delta_2 x^2 + \dots + \delta_n x^n) \\ &= (\mu_0 + \delta_0) + (\mu_1 + \delta_1)x + (\mu_2 + \delta_2)x^2 + \dots + (\mu_n + \delta_n)x^n \end{aligned}$$

which is a polynomial of degree at most $n \geq 0$.

Thus, $\mathbf{p} + \mathbf{q} \in P_n$.

Axiom 4 (**A4**):

$\mathbf{0} = 0 + 0x + 0x^2 + 0x^3 + \dots + 0x^n$, (So zero vector is in P_n).

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbf{p} + \mathbf{0})(x) &= \mathbf{p}(x) + \mathbf{0} = (\mu_0 + 0) + (\mu_1 + 0)x + (\mu_2 + 0)x^2 + \dots + (\mu_n + 0)x^n \\ &= \mu_0 + \mu_1 x + \mu_2 x^2 + \dots + \mu_n x^n = \mathbf{p}(x) \text{ and so } \mathbf{p} + \mathbf{0} = \mathbf{p}. \end{aligned}$$

Axiom 6 (**A6**):

Let s be scalar. Then $(sp)(x) = sp(x)$

$$= (s\mu_0) + (s\mu_1)x + (s\mu_2)x^2 + \dots + (s\mu_n)x^n \text{ which is in } P_n.$$

Note that the other 7 axioms (Axioms **A1**, **A4** and **A6** were formed above) also exist in P_n .

Hence, P_n is a vector space.

Note that P_n with complex numbers in the form of $\mu_a + i\mu_b$ is a vector space.

4. Conclusion

In this article, vector space was formed on the binomial coefficients of combinatorial geometric series under addition and multiplication. This new idea can enable the scientific researchers for research and development further.

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